

NEGATIVE CONSEQUENCES OF NON-SECTARIAN IDEAS AND THE IMPORTANCE OF PREVENTION

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Annotation: This article analyzes the formation of the idea of non-sectarianism, which rejects sects in Islam, its negative consequences and prevention problems in the context of philosophy.

Keywords: society, tolerance, religion, Sharia, Sunnah, imam, enlightenment, harmony, confession

Today, the divine instructions of the Islamic religion are important in ensuring peace and stability in the society by calling people to kindness, tolerance and cooperation. Currently, there is a revival of non-sectarian views, and under the influence of false ideas, the Islamic religion appears in the world community as the most complex and surprisingly full of conflicts among the world's religions in terms of fiqh sects and political currents. At the same time as the claims of religious fundamentalism to return the Islamic religion to its early period, the rejection of certain categories of fiqh sects has negative consequences in social relations. After all, the true path to faith is through understanding the divine books, the revelations and instructions of God, who revealed this religion, and Prophet Muhammad.

Allah Almighty says in the Holy Quran: “If you do not know, ask the people of Dikr” [1:624]. In this sense, in the early days of the Islamic religion, Muslims were educated by asking Muhammad about the issues they did not know about faith, knowledge of the word, and Shariah law. Later, this tradition was inherited by the scholars and young people received education from them. After that, it became a tradition for people who did not reach a certain level in Shariah sciences to follow the paths of certain scholars, and jurisprudential sects increased. The Prophet of God Muhammad also spoke about the issues we face in life: “First of all, turn to the book

of God - Kalamullah, and follow what it says, if you cannot find a solution to a problem in the Quran, then refer to the Sunnah that I left behind, and if you do not find it in the hadiths, follow what my Companions said, because my companions are like a star on the road”[3:21]. In this regard, Sheikh Muhammad Sadiq says “The first fatwa-giver was the Messenger of Allah, peace and blessings be upon him. After him, learned companions, subordinates and mujtahids became fatwa givers.” – [4:132].

As a result of the conflicts that arose in the Muslim community after the death of the Prophet Muhammad, three main sects emerged: sunni, shia and kharijites. Later, the problems of understanding the original content of the Quran and interpreting the hadiths were observed. As a result, a number of jurisprudential sects were formed within the Islamic religion. In this regard, researcher A. Tulepov states the following, “In addition to mujtahid jurists, many scholars of jurisprudence have passed through the Islamic world, but because all their creative works were perfectly collected and not presented in the form of a book, they did not gain fame as the owner of an independent sect” [4:27].

But over time, among them, four major sects: Hanafism, Malikism, Shafiism and Hanbalism were separated, and all scholars agreed on the correctness of these sects. In this regard, Allama Ibn Rajab said in his book “Rejection of those who follow other than the four schools of thought”: “Allah, the Exalted, raised four great imams from among the people with his wisdom to preserve the Sharia and protect the religion. All scholars have unanimously recognized that they have reached a high position in science and enlightenment and that their fatwas and rulings are very close to the truth. All judgments were passed through them” [4]. Based on the above analyzes and opinions, we can conclude that it is necessary to follow a sect in Islam and follow it according to the instructions of Sharia. Unfortunately, people who reject the sects in our society by misunderstanding the knowledge of the Word, denying the Sunnah and Fiqh, influence the worldview of many people and especially the youth through false claims.

Today, in different countries, you can find people who are calling to not follow sects and to follow the modernized form of religious belief in matters of Sharia. In this process, the purpose of pretending to be the “Imam” of the sect lies in the thirst for fame, financial interests, as well as preparing the population, especially the youth, for various radical ideas, religious fundamentalism and extremism.

Because, at first, the decline of the sects was strongly influenced by the reform movement of Muhammad ibn Abd al-Wahhab (1703-1792), who denied their legitimacy and called for direct reading of the Qur'anic texts. Another religious reformer, Muhammad Abdo, who was inspired by his ideas, called for rejection of taqlid by following the instructions of mujtahids of any sect. The sects were replaced not by the rationalist and liberal Islam promoted mainly by Muhammad Abdo, but by the interpretation of Islam by various figures such as Hasan al-Banna, and later by the most influential variant of wahhabism.

Many later radical reformers, from the Islamic reformer Rashid Reed (1865-1935) to the founder of the Muslim Brotherhood, Hasan al-Banna (1906-1949), promoted their vision of a sectarian Islam. In this sense, the radical “reforms” of the above persons who rejected the sects are manifested in the practices of extremism and terrorism under the guise of religion, committed in the recent history of many nations.

At the end of the 20th century, in the conditions of the rise of religious freedom, wide paths were opened for religious tolerance and inter-ethnic harmony among many confessions in Central Asia. But at the same time, the idea of non-sectarianism also came into the region. His “imams” managed to convince a number of Muslims of their false but apparently beautiful calling.

Attempts to discredit the Hanafi sect, which has been in practice for a long time in Central Asia, have led to conflicts and disagreements among Muslims. As a result, “cadres” prone to religious radicalism appeared under its influence. Taking advantage of this, malicious forces of various extremist spirit entered the region from

abroad and merged with scattered nameless sects. In this sense, we can take examples of “Hizbut Tahrir”, “Akromiya” and other extremist groups.

Researcher A. Tulepov, commenting on the idea of non-sectarianism of the Akromites, says that “their views are far from Islamic law and jurisprudence, and they make the whole world a “land of disbelief” – “darul harb”, declared war against Islamic values. Its leader, Akrom Yoldoshev, says that “the goal can be achieved by changing the opinions of all great imams”. [5:242].

Today, the ideological threats of the idea of non-sectarianism, which is corrupted within religious beliefs, continue to threaten Central Asia, including Uzbekistan. The problems of the fight against his inhumane ideas are becoming urgent and require the development of a strategic program. For this, it is necessary to develop creative and innovative methods of explaining to young people the harmful consequences of being deceived by false ideas in religious beliefs and to take measures to implement them on time. In this regard, the head of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev says “In order for common sense and healthy power to be the priority in our society, we need to regularly think and actively work to improve our spiritual life, protect the population, especially the youth, from various harmful influences, and educate them to become mature people in all aspects” [2:277]. In this process, it is necessary to pay attention to the following aspects in the practical and spiritual-educational work of youth education:

- paying special attention to events related to the spiritual heritage of the history of Central Asian socio-philosophical thinking in order to raise the practical methods of spiritual education to a new level in educational institutions;
- development of a strategic program aimed at preventing the spread of destructive ideas of religious content, "attractive" images and media products that lead young people astray through the global Internet network;
- increasing the effectiveness of the concept of “enlightenment against ignorance” by strengthening the role of the public in youth education;

- strengthening the immunity of young people against false religious views and attitudes that are spread in the form of media in social networks in the form of “mass culture” and forming an Internet culture for them.

In conclusion, false ideas such as non-sectarianism and bigotry should not threaten the education of young people in world science, the manifestation of their intellectual potential, and the rise of their spiritual and scientific worldview. For this, in the fight against these threats, we need to form a strong immunity in their hearts, and further strengthen the ideas of patriotism, peace-loving, religious tolerance and inter-ethnic harmony in them.

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